

Jupyter4NFDI

A central JupyterHub providing access to various software stacks and computing and data resources across the NFDI consortia

Proposal for the Integration Phase of Base4NFDI

Submitted: April 23rd, 2025

On behalf of: WG Research Software Engineering, Section Common Infrastructures

1 General Information

- Name of proposed Basic Service (in English)
A central JupyterHub for the NFDI
- Acronym of the proposed Basic Service
Jupyter4NFDI
- Service "subtitle" explaining key functionality
A central JupyterHub providing access to various software stacks and computing and data resources across the NFDI consortia
- Corresponding NFDI Section
Common Infrastructures
- Lead institution
Forschungszentrum Jülich GmbH, 52425 Jülich
- Name of lead institution principal investigator
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- Participating institutions

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Table 1: List of participating institutions

- Initialisation Phase

The initialisation phase started on **June 1st, 2024** and will last until **September 30th, 2025**.

- Planned duration of the integration phase

We ask for an immediate start of the integration phase on **October 1st, 2025** and envision a two year duration until **September 30th, 2027**.

- Statement on efforts required by consortia for integration of service

The central service should be immediately usable by most consortia. However, some aspects may be considered when tailoring the service for their specific requirements, primarily the integration of consortia-specific libraries and software packages. The platform has been enabled to include these requirements during the initialisation phase, where a feature to support the execution of custom Docker images and Binder-ready software repositories in the Jupyter environment has been introduced. This will be the baseline of support. Similarly, the enabling of custom software stacks on specific resources, e.g. HPC software modules, is also supported. Depending on prior usage of such environments within the consortium, such a setup would have to be transferred to the resources.

Secondly, depending on the consortium-specific entitlements to the usage of specific resources, an integration with the community AAI beyond mere authentication may be required. Jupyter4NFDI is ready to support various scenarios in this area in collaboration with IAM4NFDI.

- Summary of the proposal in English and German

Deutsch:

Jupyter ist ein wichtiger Pfeiler, um nachvollziehbare und reproduzierbare wissenschaftliche Ergebnisse zu erreichen. Ebenso bietet die Plattform Zugang zu diversen Rechen- und Datenressourcen, die über einen einheitlichen Einstiegspunkt, den JupyterHub, für die wissenschaftliche Gemeinschaft in Deutschland und darüber hinaus erreichbar sind. Während der Initialisierungsphase des Services wurden mehrere vorbereitende Ziele erreicht, die nun weitergehend in den NFDI-Konsortien, einzelnen Anwendungsfällen und wissenschaftlichen Communities integriert werden können. Ebenso können weitere externe Ressourcen hinzugefügt werden. Beides soll durch Aufrufe für Inkubatorprojekte erreicht werden, die im Projektverlauf gemeinsam mit den Interessenten durchgeführt werden.

Des Weiteren werden wir den Dienst als Reaktion auf Anfragen aus den Inkubatorprojekten weiterentwickeln. Dieser Ansatz hat sich bereits in der Anfangsphase bewährt und zu Funktionen wie der repo2docker-Integration, der Verwendung benutzerdefinierter Docker-Images und Freigabelinks für Jupyter-Konfigurationen geführt. Auf dieser soliden Basis werden wir Inhalte generieren, die im Rahmen eigener Trainings von Nutzenden und Multiplikatoren in den Communities verwendet werden. Die Inhalte befassen sich mit den FAIR-Prinzipien und wie diese

mit Hilfe von Jupyter umgesetzt werden können. Dabei werden auch fachspezifische Informationen und bewährte Methoden aus den Konsortien integriert.

English:

Jupyter is an important pillar for achieving comprehensible and reproducible scientific results. The platform also provides access to various computing and data resources that can be accessed via a single entry point, the JupyterHub, for the scientific community in Germany and beyond. During the initialisation phase of the service, several preparatory goals were achieved, which can now be further integrated in the NFDI consortia, individual use cases and scientific communities. Likewise, further external resources can be integrated. Both will be achieved through calls for incubator projects, which will be carried out together with interested parties during the course of the project.

Furthermore, we will continue to develop the service in response to requests from researchers, consortia and, particularly, the incubator projects. This approach has already proven successful in the initial phase and has led to features such as the repo2docker integration, the use of custom Docker images and shareable links for Jupyter configurations. On this sound basis, we will generate content that can be used for end-user and multiplier training in the communities. The content addresses Jupyter itself, the FAIR principles and how they can be implemented using Jupyter. Domain-specific information and best practices from the consortia will also be integrated.

2 Summary of Initialisation Phase Results

2.1 Change in Background and Motivation since the Start of the Initialisation Phase

The TEC evaluation of our proposal for the Initialisation Phase mentioned two major concerns revolving around policies for resource access and key performance indicators to assess effectiveness and utility of the basic service. We will try to respond to these in the following.

It is important to distinguish access to the Jupyter service and access to the resources behind it. There is a tendency to confuse these two, and users who have access to the service, e.g. by being able to log in, may falsely believe that this should grant them access to all resources connected to the service. We agree that the access policy and how to apply for more resources must be clearly defined and communicated. A dedicated section within the service's documentation has been created to address this situation and will be extended as the service develops and more resources will be added to it.¹

The definition of appropriate KPIs is part of this proposal as requested by the template and will be dealt with in section 3.1.5.

¹ Resource access and available systems <https://nfdi-jupyter.de/features/#1-systems-available>

Furthermore, all consortia were asked about their current needs with respect to the service, their intention to pursue an own development, and general comments about the Jupyter4NFDI service and approach. This provided some valuable insights about consortia requirements that we would like to respond to in this proposal.

We also received feedback from consortia after submission of the proposal for the initialisation phase. Several of them indicated requirements from the areas of data access, custom containers, education and training, and FAIR principles. Further requirements mentioned by individual responses referred to IAM, federation, resource access, parallelisation, PIDs, workflows, legal framework and privacy.

This is also supported by the results of the survey that we conducted between December 2024 and January 2025, cf. requirements analysis D1.4.1 in section 2.2.1.

Some of these aspects are already covered in the existing basic service today, whereas others will receive attention during the integration phase. For example, custom containers can already be used within the service today, offering great flexibility to users. A generic data access mechanism is under development.

2.2 Results of Initialisation Phase

The central service² has been put in place already in July 2024. Initially, it provides access to IaaS Cloud resources at Jülich Supercomputing Centre (JSC), co-located with the central hub. By popular demand, the hub configuration has been extended with the following features:

- **Share links**³ allow to reference ready-to-use Jupyter configurations.
- **Custom Docker images**⁴ allow to provide and use specific software environments that would otherwise not be covered by the default settings.
- The **Repo2Docker**⁵ functionality facilitates building Docker images directly from GitHub, GitLab, Zenodo or other sources.

An additional environment for the preparation of new resource integrations or feature evaluations has been made available⁶. Among other things, it currently provides access to resources at Max Planck Computing and Data Facility (MPCDF). Similarly, cloud resources from our partner TU Dresden have been made available and the integration of High-Performance Computing (HPC) resources of the Verein für Nationales Hochleistungsrechnen (NHR)⁷ is in preparation.

2 Central JupyterHub <https://hub.nfdi-jupyter.de/>

3 Share link documentation <https://nfdi-jupyter.de/users/misc/#share-button>

4 Custom Docker images <https://nfdi-jupyter.de/users/jupyterlab/customdockerimage/>

5 Repo2Docker <https://nfdi-jupyter.de/users/jupyterlab/repo2docker/>

6 Staging environment <https://hub-staging.nfdi-jupyter.de/>

7 Verein für Nationales Hochleistungsrechnen <https://www.nhr-verein.de/>

Towards the end of 2024, we have published a survey targeted at potential stakeholders of our infrastructure. Despite the fact that Jupyter is an established service in many communities, our intention is to have the best possible coverage of relevant use cases.

The project website⁸ has been put in place, providing information about the infrastructure. The domain had previously been used to host an inventory of available Jupyter services within the NFDI, which is still available as part of the site.

Based on input from various user groups, the basic service appears to be already usable for their use cases. Usage statistics of the service from the initial release until recently indicate a growing interest in using the service⁹.

2.2.1 Interim Report on Requirements for Finalisation of the Initialisation Phase

a) Requirements Analysis (D1.4.1)

Due: 3 months after start date

Percent finished: 100%

Status: report / finished

Overview of relevant outcomes:

A survey was opened in December 2024 and ran until January 9, 2025. 75 participants from 53 German research institutions provided their answers. The survey responses revealed awareness of and interest in Jupyter4NFDI across diverse institutions. Participants emphasized the platform's value in lowering technical barriers, enabling reproducibility, and offering a reliable alternative to local setups. The results highlight the broad relevance of Jupyter4NFDI and support further expansion and user-driven development during the upcoming integration phase. The results of this survey have been made available in two forms. First of all, we have a summary document that is hosted as a GitHub page¹⁰. On this GitHub page, we link to our very own Jupyter service with a launch button, leading to an interactive execution of the summary generation. This can be used for a more thorough analysis or query the survey data about new questions.

b) Software Evaluation (D1.4.2)

Due: 6 months after start date

Percent finished: 100%

⁸ Jupyter4NFDI project web site <https://nfdi-jupyter.de/>

⁹ Jupyter4NFDI usage statistics <https://zenodo.org/records/15187218>

¹⁰ Survey result summary https://gesiscss.github.io/Jupyter4NFDI_survey_results/Jupyter4NFDI%20Survey%20Summary.html

Status: finished

Overview of relevant outcomes:

The central part of the software stack for the Jupyter4NFDI service is a quite natural choice, as Jupyter is taken for granted. There are multiple ways in which a central JupyterHub can be deployed. One of them is a Kubernetes (K8S) environment. Whereas this is not essential for the end users, it is still useful during the operation of a large-scale JupyterHub, because this deployment model provides for some level of fault-tolerance without the intervention of administrators, leading to higher uptimes and a more reliable service.

The two central pieces of software, of which rudimentary versions were available at the onset of the project, are the JupyterHub Outpost¹¹ and the corresponding JupyterHub OutpostSpawner¹². These components provide for a flexible solution involving multiple types of resources that can all be accessed from the single hub.

Outlook: There are individual software solutions appearing regularly that share some functionality with Jupyter. In some cases, these can even be integrated with the central service to complement the overall functionality. At other times, they are simply comparable solutions. We will monitor the landscape to identify opportunities. Notable candidates for this are VSCode, R-Studio, MATLAB and XPra, to name a few.

c) **Service Design (D1.4.3)**

Due: 6 months after start date

Percent finished: 100

Status: report / finished

Overview of relevant outcomes: The service design has been documented as part of the project web site and user documentation. Relevant links can be found in the appendix (OpenProject status report).

Outlook: Additional requirements from NFDI consortia or other users will be monitored and, if need be, will influence the service design and further development of the service.

d) **Service Prototype (D1.4.4)**

Due: 12 months after start date

Percent finished: 100%

Status: finished

11 JupyterHub Outpost: <https://zenodo.org/records/14616149>

12 JupyterHub OutpostSpawner: <https://zenodo.org/records/14616171>

Overview of relevant outcomes: the central hub has been deployed¹³ and documentation for users and interested resource providers is available at our central website¹⁴.

Outlook: maintenance and further development of the service will be the subject of WP1 described in section 5.2.1.

e) Service Piloting and User Testing (D1.4.5)

Due: 12 months after start date

Percent finished: 50

Status: running

Overview of relevant outcomes: The service has been tested in several consortia regarding its applicability for end users. At the same time, we are in the process of onboarding additional external resources. More details can be found in the attached OpenProject report.

Outlook: For an accepted service like this, there is a natural feedback loop with users establishing requirements towards the service. In addition to the regular consultation hours for external resource providers, we will also offer separate consultation hours for end users of our service in the future. The idea is to have a low entry barrier for users and maybe discuss prepared topics arising from specific requests that may be of broader interest.

2.2.2 Other

During the first nine months of the project, members of the project team attended several workshops and events to present their ideas and the current status of the project. On July 15, Jupyter4NFDI was presented within an NFDI Talk¹⁵. The project was also represented at the 1st Base4NFDI User Conference in November, and at the Base4NFDI Roadshow in December. Project representatives also visited consortia meetings of non-participating consortia. For example, Jupyter4NFDI was presented at the MaRDI Service Marketplace during the MaRDI annual meeting in Kaiserslautern in November 2024 and the Text+ Show and Tell series of talks in January 2025.

2.3 Update on Technical Readiness Level (TRL) of the Proposed Basic Service

During preparations for this proposal, the TRL levels of several key components have been reassessed based on their stability, functionality, and integration into the production environment.

- **JupyterHub @ JSC and OutpostSpawner** has been upgraded from TRL 7 to TRL 8. The system has demonstrated its stability beyond the prototype phase and has proven to be a reliable solution for the project's evolving needs.

13 Central JupyterHub <https://hub.nfdi-jupyter.de/>

14 Jupyter4NFDI web site: <https://nfdi-jupyter.de/>

15 NFDI Talk Jupyter4NFDI: <https://zenodo.org/records/14162496>

- **JupyterHub Outpost** has also been raised from TRL 7 to TRL 8. Since its introduction, it has consistently delivered on its intended purpose, managing notebook servers and other web services across various JupyterHub spawners and systems. Its reliability and maturity justify the higher TRL.
- **JupyterHub Binder Integration** has been elevated from TRL 6 to TRL 7. The initial production deployment has evolved into a fully integrated solution, enabling seamless reproducibility through Binder-ready repositories.
- **BinderHub deployment** of GESIS, as part of the MyBinder federation, is at TRL 8, and the uptime of the deployment is tracked via dedicated site reliability monitoring.¹⁶
- **IAM4NFDI** will be integrated during the end of the initialisation phase. Its TRL level will be updated once it has been actively used and evaluated within the project.

These adjustments reflect the progress made during the initialisation phase of the project and set the foundation for the upcoming development and expansion of these services.

Furthermore, the service team is regularly contributing to the generic Jupyter service, as demonstrated by several merged or active pull requests on GitHub, cf. details in Bibliography and List of References. Compared to the situation at the start of the initialisation phase, this leads to the comfortable situation that all customisations of the central service can now be done through configuration rather than code changes.

Component	TRL	Description
OpenStack, Kubernetes, Rancher, Fleet, JupyterHub	9	External developments
UNICORE	8	Development for over 25 years at JSC and external partners
JupyterHub @ JSC and OutpostSpawner	8	JupyterHub instance and custom Spawner (in operation since 2017)
JupyterHub Outpost	8	RestAPI to manage notebook-server and other web services for every JupyterHub spawner (in operation since 2017 and 2021 respectively with a different name)
JupyterHub-Binder Integration	7	Allows the persistent import of binder-ready repositories into the JupyterHub from platforms such as GitHub.
BinderHub as part of MyBinder federation	8	BinderHub deployment for the lightweight reproducibility of binder-ready repositories as part of the MyBinder federation.
IAM4NFDI	5	External development, average of components as indicated by the IAM4NFDI proposal with technical solutions already at TRL 9

¹⁶ <https://mybinder.readthedocs.io/en/latest/about/status.html>

3 Working Concept for the Development of the Basic Service

3.1 Service Integration Concept

The overall goal of Jupyter4NFDI is the support of FAIR research with a particular focus on reproducibility, supported by a seamless and efficient service that integrates with various NFDI consortia and basic services. To this end, we have identified a number of targets for offering the service during the integration phase.

3.1.1 Targets

The primary target users of our service are the NFDI **consortia and their represented communities**. There are already collaborations ongoing with several consortia, including those in which the principal investigators of Jupyter4NFDI are active. Engagement with consortia will be two-fold. First of all, end users within the consortia will use our service on a daily basis to conduct their research. Secondly, special demands in some consortia go beyond the provisioning of a plain Jupyter service. We will collaborate with these consortia to accommodate such demanding use cases. The precise topics of collaboration will be defined on a case-by-case basis, as they are highly specific.

The second target of our service will be integrations with **other basic services** to provide additional features or enhanced services. To this end, we have initiated contacts with the corresponding service teams. Preliminary details of potential collaborations can be found in section 3.1.3 below.

The third target will be the integration of **external resources** that we will onboard and to which the central service will provide access in a seamless manner. The technical approach for this has been proven to be viable during the initialisation phase, in which we integrated Cloud Computing resources of the MPCDF¹⁷, de.NBI Cloud¹⁸ and NHR HPC resources at TU Dresden¹⁹. The integration of Cloud resources at JSC²⁰ provided the basis for this and are also available as part of the offering.

We are aware that NFDI has been selected as a candidate node for the **EOSC**, and will continue to monitor developments and adapt our service accordingly. We believe that our service will be complementary to existing EOSC services and will provide a unique offering for all users. Moreover, partner JSC is an indirect member of the EOSC Beyond project through the EUDAT CDI and has a share in the development of the NFDI EOSC Pilot node.

17 HPC Cloud resources at MPCDF: <https://docs.mpcdf.mpg.de/doc/cloud/index.html>

18 de.NBI Cloud resources at University of Bielefeld: <https://cloud.denbi.de/about/>

19 NHR HPC resources at TU Dresden <https://tu-dresden.de/zh/hochleistungsrechnen/nhr-center>

20 JSC Cloud resources: <https://apps.fz-juelich.de/jsc/hps/jsccloud/>

3.1.2 Measures

We intend to reach the above mentioned targets through several measures, referring to the work packages (WPs) defined in Section 5.

First of all, coordinated by WP5, we will conduct **incubator projects** in collaboration with the respective target groups. This approach has been premiered by IAM4NFDI and constitutes a sensible framework for starting new integrations. As we have identified several target groups, we will run specific incubators tailored to each of them, such that end users will be handled differently from other services and external resources. There will be calls for **use-case incubators** targeting users of our platform, end users and content providers alike. Content providers could provide software stacks or specific configurations that will be easily re-usable on the Jupyter4NFDI platform, such as best practice environments for recurring approaches within the consortium or community. Another type of incubator will target **additional resources providers** such as **NHR** centres or **Cloud** providers such as a potential future **NFDI Multi-Cloud**²¹. A prototypical NHR integration has been created together with partner TU Dresden during the initialisation phase.

Secondly, we will increase activities to **create and integrate content** (WP4) dedicated to various stakeholder groups. These groups will comprise end users, trainers and resource providers. For reasons of efficiency, the re-use of content is very important. We will team up with the NFDI Section EduTrain²² to make content available via the knowledge base **DALIA** and also serve as an environment for interactive training materials as well as during training activities of the recent basic service RDMTraining4NFDI. Furthermore, ample material is already available from either external sources or team members. This will also be re-used and made available in the appropriate locations.

Lastly, our content will be used in our **own training and outreach activities** (WP5) as well as the training activities of external groups. To this end, we will continue to attend consortia meetings to present the Jupyter4NFDI basic service and get in contact with potential user groups. This will also provide opportunities to gather feedback to improve the service and realise challenging new use cases together with the user groups.

3.1.3 Basic Services

The integration with some of the other basic services stands out from the above mentioned measures and shall be mentioned here separately. Initial discussions already provided some ideas for potential integration with several basic services.

We will collaborate with **nfdi.software** to enhance the user experience for finding suitable software components for their task. This can involve using a software search API provided by nfdi.software

²¹ NFDI Multi-Cloud: <https://zenodo.org/records/6510971> . We mention Multi-Cloud as an example, being fully aware that the Base4NFDI Multi-Cloud service will not be available in the near future.

²² <https://www.nfdi.de/section-edutrain/>

to search by certain criteria. Moreover, the registration of software in the catalogue can be used to directly link to executable software environments in Jupyter. The goal is to find significantly more software configurations for reuse than could be provided by Jupyter4NFDI alone. In an ever more complex software landscape that stretches operating systems, specific hardware, and also domain specific codes, **Terminology Service (TS)** can help users in finding the right configuration for their task at hand.

The envisioned collaboration with **PID4NFDI** can take on two forms. For one, references to data or software may be integrated into Jupyter by means of a standard library that helps in the resolution and subsequent retrieval of such resources from the Jupyter environment. Furthermore, Jupyter configurations can be referenced and enriched with metadata through PIDs, which then paves the way for their integration in knowledge graphs. The integration with a future **Knowledge Graph Infrastructure (KGI)** will benefit from this PID integration.

3.1.4 External Resources and Services

There are some additional resources and services that do not fall into any of the above mentioned categories. The integration of external data and software repositories will include DataVerse and CKAN. We will also evaluate the integration of the Methods Hub at GESIS²³. The BinderHub instance will ensure the service's participation in the MyBinder federation²⁴.

3.1.5 Business Model and KPIs

The **operation of the central service** is only part of the overall activities within the project. For the time being and in the foreseeable future, this will be handled by JSC staff using resources provided by JSC. We will ensure that the central service can be deployed elsewhere, for example in a public Cloud provider or potential NFDI Multi-Cloud, to avoid a provider lock-in.

Ongoing **support activities**, such as a service specific help desk or training and education activities, will have to be funded in the long run. This can be handled through a paid service or through central funding if available in the long run.

With the central service facilitating access to various **external resources**, the operational model of these resources must also be considered. Regarding access to HPC computing, which is available through the NHR, it is up to the users to request access to these resources, which can subsequently be used through the central Jupyter service. However, we will provide guidance as to where users can and should apply for resources and how to do so.

To ensure that our service can scale to meet the needs of a larger user group, we will monitor technical and organisational key performance indicators (KPIs), including: number of connected

23 GESIS Methods Hub https://www.nfdi4datascience.de/services/gesismethodshub_d/

24 MyBinder federation <https://mybinder.readthedocs.io/en/latest/about/federation.html>

resources providers, number of connected consortia, number of participants in Jupyter4NFDI trainings, overall amount of CPUs, RAM, GPUs, and storage, statistics on the CPU, RAM, and GPU resource requirements from actual user sessions, number of active users / sessions per period. Expected numbers for the given KPIs will be defined as part of the mandatory Base4NFDI deliverable D2.4.4 “Admission of a service to service portfolio”. Aggregated data of the technical KPIs above will be exposed to end users via a status page. At the same time, usage data will be collected to integrate with EOSC and provide service access based on **EOSC Core Node Credits**.

3.1.6 Partner Consortia

In **Text+**, the Jupyter4NFDI service is being used regularly for at least one use case: The Fluffy Import. This involves a notebook-based application for importing data in TextGridRep²⁵. The notebook-based approach replaces the initial import and publication system, which became difficult to maintain and update. The NFDI JupyterHub is the recommended platform for running the application, and a link to a preconfigured environment based on a Docker image is provided in the readme of the code repository. Furthermore, there is a high level of interest in the various consortia in using the service to organise workshops, which was also evident when Base4NFDI presented the service at conferences. In addition to important existing features such as resource auto-scaling during periods of high demand, the feedback gathered from completed workshops will help improve the service for future events.

In the **NFDI4DS** consortium, Jupyter4NFDI plays a central role as an execution backed for computational analysis pipelines frequently used in the area of Data Science. These pipelines follow the literate coding paradigm and are published as Jupyter notebooks on GitHub along with the necessary dependencies. The key service for NFDI4DS in this context is the Methods Hub, a publication platform for data science methods published in the format of notebooks. As part of the incubator program, users of the Methods Hub will be enabled to launch interactive method implementations on Jupyter4NFDI using the repo2docker import capability.

The consortium **NFDI4ING** reflects the importance of Jupyter services for RDM in engineering. A dedicated JupyterHub²⁶ has been installed in its first funding period and several Jupyter-related measures have been proposed for the second period. In particular, a specific task “Jup4ING” is outlined in the proposal that is shared between multiple NFDI4ING task areas and aims to integrate NFDI4ING services in the Jupyter ecosystem. All respective activities will be aligned with Jupyter4NFDI, particularly, by connecting the consortium’s hub to the central instance.

Activities in the **MaRDI** consortium include efforts dedicated at assessing the computational reproducibility of mathematical software, including but not limited to Jupyter notebooks. In mathematics, a wide variety of programming languages is used, many of which have Jupyter

²⁵ <https://textgridrep.org/>

²⁶ <https://jupyter.nfdi4ing.de>

kernels, while some don't. MaRDI can thus assist in providing example notebooks in languages other than Julia, Python and R. In the MaRDI portal, knowledge graph-powered profiles are being developed for a variety of mathematical research objects, again including but not limited to Jupyter notebooks.

3.2 Future Development and Ramp-Up Outlook

The Jupyter4NFDI service is technically already quite advanced now. Its precursor has been operating reliably for several years before the onset of the basic service project. Users can expect a high quality of service with high uptime.

We are already working with Base4NFDI's legal experts regarding challenges that occur due to the integration of external resources. The final service will have answers to these challenges and inform users about the relations between the central service and external resources, a key requirement of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)²⁷.

More than educational material and trainings provided by the project, the day-to-day use of a service will require proper support structures. This will be facilitated by establishing links to the consortia help desks²⁸, who can delegate service specific requests, be it technical problems or requests for specific consultation, to Jupyter4NFDI staff.

While developing the service, we will pay attention to multiple facets of sustainability. For instance, we will build on pilot projects that assessed the environmental footprint of Jupyter notebooks, and we will use the existing corpus of notebooks and containerized environments to assess reproducibility decay over time, so as to develop robust criteria for which reproducibility measures we will be supporting, how and on what time scales.

3.3 Risks and Challenges

Several consortia have built up their own services that are quite comparable to our central service. While our declared goal is to integrate these services in the offerings of the central hub, there is a risk that they remain isolated, despite limited availability and barriers hindering general accessibility. Certain scenarios that we consider essential for FAIR science are frequently not possible with the existing services, e.g. sharing results publicly from within the service, violating at least the accessibility and reusability aspects.

Similarly, resource providers within consortia are already serving their users' needs. It may be difficult to convince them to participate in a more open approach that makes the resources and scientific results available to a wider audience. On the other hand, NFDI itself does not provide

²⁷ General Data Protection Regulation <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:02016R0679-20160504>

²⁸ Consortia help desks <https://www.nfdi.de/helpdesks/>

funding for physical resources, primarily storage and servers, and therefore we consider a central basic service favourable in the competition for available resources and their integration.

Furthermore, an evaluation of the legal challenges of the central service led to the insight that **a central service is also preferable over many fragmented services**, because if users turn to consortia-specific, local, or even external (potentially untrusted) services instead of Jupyter4NFDI, this could bring more problems and complications. Also, a fragmented system leads to inconsistencies, less interoperability, and potential security risks.

4 Support Actions from Base4NFDI / NFDI Sections, and Integrating NFDI Consortia / Efforts (max 1 page)

Support from	Work package / Description of contribution	Contact person Basic Service
Base4NFDI	Support organising workshop/training, promotion	André Giesler, a.giesler@fz-juelich.de
Base4NFDI Training TA 4	Development of training material	Antje Manske
Base4NFDI	User research and evaluation for Jupyter4NFDI products and prototypes	Tianying Chen, GESIS, tianying.chen@gesis.org Brigitte Mathiak, GESIS, brigitte.mathiak@gesis.org
EduTrain/DALIA	Hosting of domain specific training materials	Sonja Herres-Pawlis
RDMTraining4NFDI	Integration of training material with Jupyter4NFDI, e.g., direct usage links, trainings and workshops on the hub	Mareike Wohltmann
nfdi.software	Integration of software with Jupyter4NFDI, e.g., direct usage links	Marc Hanisch
Knowledge Graph Infrastructure	FAIRJupyter Knowledge Graph, use of Jupyter notebooks for exploring NFDI knowledge graphs	Daniel Mietchen

Table 2: Support needed from Base4NFDI / Service Stewards / Section

Support from	Involved effort	Consortium (contact)
NFDI4DS	Users of JupyterHub and	Sonja Schimmler,

	connected resources. Provider of ecosystem of re-usable materials.	sonja.schimmeler@fokus.fraunhofer.de
Text+	Content provider, maintenance of consortium's Fluffy Import.	George Dogaru
NFDI4ING	Shared task "Jup4ING". See LoC for details.	Peter Pelz, peter.pelz@tu-darmstadt.de
MaRDI	Assessment of computational reproducibility of mathematical software.	Daniel Mietchen

Table 3: Contributions required from the integrating consortia

5 Work Programme (ca. 6 pages)

5.1 Overview of Work Packages

The project is divided into five work packages only partially overlapping with work packages from the initialisation phase. WP1 will be largely dedicated to the maintenance and development of the basic service, comparable to WP1 of the initialisation phase. The resource manager interface has been defined and its maintenance and updates will also be covered by WP1. The new WP2 will deal with the integration into the AAI landscape. Part of this will already happen towards the end of the still ongoing initialisation phase, but we do expect a more fine grained authorisation infrastructure for resource access to be required by some communities. WP3 will be about the integration of additional resources to the basic service. In WP4, we will create user-oriented training material as plain documentation as well as exemplary setups or Jupyter Notebooks for various user groups. WP5 remains dedicated to dissemination and the integration into the wider Jupyter ecosystem. We provide details about the work packages in the following sections.

Work package	Deliverables (D) and milestones (M)	Responsible partner and participants
1. Maintenance and development of service	D1.1 Persistent import API D1.2 BinderHub instance as part of the MyBinder federation D1.3 FAIRJupyter deployed M1.1 All components for Content integration are available M1.2 Parameterised execution of JupyterLab	JSC GESIS, FIZ

	M1.3 Provide public available KPIs	
2. AAI integration	M2.1 Integration of IAM infrastructure proxy M2.2. Integration of consortium specific permission structures D2.1 Documentation of entitlements and permissions D2.2 Updated documentation of entitlements and permissions	GWDG JSC, TUD
3. Integration of additional resources	D3.1 Extended partner tutorials D3.2 Hands-on support in onboarding external resources M3.1 Integration template repository	MPCDF TUD, US
4. Content integration	D4.1 Use cases featuring fully computationally reproducible content D4.2 Domain-independent training materials D4.3 Domain-specific adaptation of the materials M4.1 Initial version of the materials available M4.2 Final version of the materials available	GESIS FIZ, GWDG, TUD, US, TUC
5. Community engagement and communication	M5.1 First call for incubator projects D5.1 Jupyter4NFDI training material for RDMTraining4NFDI M5.2 First workshop “Make your work reproducible with Jupyter4NFDI” D5.2 Presentation material for roadshows, consortia meetings, and others	US FIZ, GESIS, GWDG

Table 4: Overall work programme with work packages, deliverables, milestones, and responsible partner.

A Gantt chart of the milestones and deliverables is provided in section 5.2.6.

5.2 Detailed Work Programme

5.2.1 WP1: Maintenance and Development of Service

WP lead: JSC

Contributors: FIZ, GESIS

The primary objective of this work package is to ensure the technical maintenance and development of the core service infrastructure, which includes the central JupyterHub and the JupyterHub Outposts. This work package is crucial for maintaining operational stability and

adapting to evolving requirements (D1.1, M1.1). It involves addressing technical issues, implementing updates, and supporting the JupyterHub Outpost interface.

WP1 will focus on several key aspects, beginning with the regular monitoring and optimisation of service performance to ensure reliability. Any technical issues that arise will be promptly addressed to minimise downtime. Additionally, audits of the service's health will be conducted regularly, and fixes will be implemented as necessary.

We will also build on the already existing KPIs²⁹ and basic performance metrics that have been established. Through integration and collaboration with IAM4NFDI, we aim to improve these indicators further. The KPIs will be made publicly available in order to increase transparency and to track the growing use and anchoring of Jupyter4NFDI in the NFDI communities (M1.3).

A significant component of WP1 is the maintenance and improvement of the JupyterHub Outpost interface and installation, which plays a crucial role in managing infrastructure resources. The work will ensure that the interface remains functional and up to date, adapting to any changes in underlying infrastructure or APIs. This includes incorporating improvements that streamline resource allocation and enhance user experience.

Another focus for WP1 is applying software patches and updates to keep dependencies secure and compatible. As new features become necessary to align with project goals, they will be integrated thoughtfully to enhance functionality and usability. One of these new features will be the parameterised start of JupyterLab. This will allow users to configure variables and add them to a specific JupyterLab configuration (M1.2). Alongside technical updates, WP1 will emphasise maintaining comprehensive documentation of the service architecture, configurations, workflows, and changes.

Another significant aspect of WP1 is the provision of a dedicated staging instance. This environment is designed to allow external resource providers to thoroughly test the integration of their resources before transitioning to the production environment of Jupyter4NFDI. The staging instance ensures that new integrations are seamless, stable, and fully compatible with the existing infrastructure. By offering a safe and controlled space for testing, this initiative minimises potential disruptions in the production environment and supports a smooth onboarding process for new resource providers.

WP1 anticipates challenges, such as managing service downtime during updates and adapting to infrastructure changes. These will be mitigated by scheduling updates during off-peak hours, implementing fallback mechanisms, and fostering regular collaboration with infrastructure teams.

Alongside the maintenance and development of the core services of Jupyter4NFDI, the work package will also ensure that complementary services are integrated into the overall Jupyter4NFDI

²⁹ Jupyter4NFDI usage statistics <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15187218>

landscape. This includes making a BinderHub instance available as part of the MyBinder federation (D1.2), or integrating the reproducibility assessment workflows of FAIRJupyter into Jupyter4NFDI (D1.3). We will continuously monitor the evolving ecosystem of tools and services, and integrate the ones that provide clear benefits to our users.

By focusing on these areas, WP1 will provide the foundational technical support required to maintain the stability and functionality of the service while ensuring it evolves in line with project objectives.

5.2.2 WP2: AAI Integration

WP lead: GWDG

Contributors: JSC, TUD

The work on integrating Jupyter4NFDI with IAM4NFDI is ongoing and happens in coordination with the IAM4NFDI project. The main goal is to extend the reach of Jupyter4NFDI so that it is usable via all community AAI which are part of IAM4NFDI, so basically the availability across all NFDI consortia is intended.

The central Jupyter4NFDI service, which was made available in a short time after the start of the project's initialisation phase, is already accessible via the Helmholtz AAI. Its role is to integrate resources from participating institutions and enable users to run Jupyter notebooks on infrastructure (JupyterHubs) available to them according to their access rights. At a technical level, the communication required to delegate work to the available hubs is realised by JupyterHub Outpost, which is well documented, including the options, adaptations, and customisations relevant for JupyterHub providers in order to communicate with the central hub and with the (current) AAI. This allows for a fine-grained control over the access to resources according to information received from the AAI.

When the NFDI Infra Proxy becomes available, the required adaptations to the service will be made in order for this to be used instead of the current AAI. In the time before this switch (and if necessary, also after), the focus will be on specifying requirements for the NFDI AAI based on the use cases that need to be or to remain supported. This can include adaptations to, and requirements for, the infrastructure proxy (M2.1), but also the community AAI (M2.2). The metadata supplied by the NFDI AAI can for example be used to allow customized access to resources depending on affiliation to a consortium or to a dedicated user group. Determining and refining appropriate AAI metadata will happen in cooperation with the IAM4NFDI service. It will also be possible to leverage the metadata in order to gain better insight into how different consortia or groups use the service and to derive relevant KPIs from it.

At a conceptual level, the work will involve translating the AAI concepts in appropriate options for the service, in formulating requirements of the service for the AAI, in helping to harmonise the options of the central service and the existing JupyterHubs and their AAIs. Another outcome of the work package will be a documentation of the AAI options and aspects of the service (D2.1, D2.2).

5.2.3 WP3: Integration of Additional Resources

WP lead: JSC

Contributors: MPCDF, TUD, US

In the project's initialisation phase, we established foundational steps, including the development of reference templates and initial documentation for resource APIs that facilitated essential external resource integration. Building on this groundwork, WP3 will focus on collaborating with external partners to integrate their resources into the Jupyter4NFDI ecosystem. This work includes guiding partners through testing on the staging instance to ensure compatibility and stability before moving to production. WP3 will also capture lessons learned and potential challenges to further refine the integration process, ultimately enhancing the overall service.

In particular, we plan to offer a variety of channels that provide extended partner-centric tutorials (D3.1) and updated integration templates (M3.1) enabling resource partners to set up their service infrastructure with a high degree of self-sufficiency as well as supporting hands-on sessions (D3.2) from the Jupyter4NFDI team.

Our next-phase documentation (D3.1) will incorporate feedback from early adopters, offer deeper technical guidance, and present best practices learned from real-world integrations, addressing common pitfalls and advanced scenarios. These refinements will accommodate a wider variety of environments, orchestration frameworks, and networking scenarios, ensuring that future partners have a smoother and more scalable path for integration.

Ultimately, it all comes together in an integration template repository (M3.1) which will offer ready-to-run solutions for resource partners. To achieve this, we will identify different computing infrastructures commonly employed at institutions, including variations in hardware architectures (HPC, Research Cloud, VMs, etc.), software stacks, orchestration frameworks (Kubernetes, OpenStack, Slurm, etc.), networking setups, and storage solutions. We will build our guidelines with this heterogeneous scientific computing landscape in mind. Especially with the prospect of an ever-growing community of JupyterHub Outpost providers, and the fact that we have a limited number of in-person support resources, this will ensure that our support efforts can truly scale with our integration pursuits. This will also reduce the time required for new partners to become operational, thereby accelerating overall adoption. Through these detailed templates, common troubleshooting steps, and robust testing guidelines, this milestone will empower both current and

future partners to set up JupyterHub Outposts effectively, thereby driving sustainable growth of the Jupyter4NFDI ecosystem.

In addition to the enhanced documentation and templates (D3.1, M3.1), we will provide direct hands-on assistance (D3.2) for new resource providers integrating their infrastructure into the Jupyter4NFDI ecosystem. This deliverable will include interactive support channels such as scheduled consultation sessions, on-demand troubleshooting, and collaborative testing on staging environments, to help institutions address challenges unique to their HPC, cloud, or specialised computing setups. By offering live guidance beyond self-service materials, D3.2 ensures that complex technical issues and edge cases can be resolved more quickly, accelerating resource integration. Moreover, insights gathered during these one-on-one engagements will continuously feed back into our documentation, templates, and best practices, further refining the overall integration experience for future partners.

Additionally, WP3 will actively explore opportunities to expand the ecosystem by identifying and engaging with potential new resource providers. Examples include collaborations with platforms such as de.NBI Cloud or Multi-Cloud infrastructures as well as centres of the NHR alliance, broadening the range of integrated resources available to the Jupyter4NFDI community. This effort will ensure that the service remains dynamic and continues to grow in alignment with project goals.

5.2.4 WP4: Content Integration

WP lead: GESIS

Contributors: FIZ, GWDG, TUD, US, TUC

With this work package, we will establish an ecosystem that supports creating, sharing and reusing computationally reproducible notebook content, along with the accompanying data, for the Jupyter4NFDI service. To this end, we will provide readily available practical training resources, templates, and use case studies to facilitate the efficient adoption and integration of the service by users across diverse domains and consortia. The core objective is to enable users to develop and disseminate computationally reusable Jupyter notebook content and data, making it available for the service. This includes identifying the necessary metadata (CPU, RAM, storage requirements, supported programming languages) to select and configure the right node with the appropriate resources and transferring notebooks and data to the node. The use cases will concentrate on standard repository platforms like GitHub, GitLab, and DataVerse. This content will be usable along with the necessary data within the Jupyter4NFDI ecosystem through three mechanisms deployed as part of WP1: 1) the Binder launch capability, 2) the JupyterHub Repo2Docker import capability, and 3) the FAIRJupyter reproducibility assessment workflow (Samuel & Mietchen, 2024a,b). These three mechanisms are interoperable with respect to the provided content but address distinct needs: exploratory lightweight launching of an interactive session (Binder), long-term content

development (Repo2Docker import) as well as running and documenting batch verification of reproducibility (FAIRJupyter).

To bootstrap such an ecosystem, we will create use cases (D.4.1) by identifying and implementing representative examples of notebook-centred content. This will include, e.g., use cases from the social sciences (GESIS), artificial intelligence (TUD with ScaDS.AI) and biomedicine (FIZ/FAIRJupyter), demonstrating the potential of Jupyter for reproducible research within the NFDI.

Based on these use cases, we will develop domain-independent training materials (D.4.2). The materials will take the form of step-by-step guides on preparing and publishing content using the Jupyter4NFDI infrastructure and lead to a template for a short workshop on ‘How to Bring Your Work to Jupyter4NFDI’ that will be usable across domains. As part of WP5, the materials will then be presented to different consortia through workshops and other formats. They will be adaptable for both self-study and instructor-led sessions. Furthermore, we will tailor the training materials to different audiences, including students and instructors, following the established Train-the-Trainer pattern. The materials for instructors will also be integrated into more general workshops, such as introductions to Python or R programming that are available through platforms like The Carpentries. Given our experience with trainings on reproducible research and Jupyter (e.g. GESIS Training Workshop 2023 ‘Workflows for Reproducible Research with R & Git’³⁰), we believe that leveraging synergies between domain-specific programming education and Jupyter notebook training maximises relevance and impact. To that end, we will also develop domain-specific training materials (D.4.3) for selected fields of study.

This work package aligns closely with other Base4NFDI initiatives focused on training materials, user story development, and persona creation. By building on existing resources and approaches, safeguard compatibility and integration with broader NFDI efforts, such as the Software Marketplace, are safeguarded.

The materials developed in this work package will lower the barrier for researchers to adopt Jupyter4NFDI for their computational analysis and promote best practices in reproducible research across the NFDI community. Feedback from the community is collected and used to improve the materials.

5.2.5 WP5: Community Engagement and Communication

WP lead: US

Contributors: FIZ, GESIS, GWDG, JSC, TUD

³⁰ <https://github.com/jobreu/reproducible-research-gesis-2023>

This work package will ensure effective interaction between our team and the diverse research communities within the NFDI, as represented by the disciplinary consortia. We will foster a collaborative environment, promoting the adoption of Jupyter-based workflows and gathering user feedback to refine the service continuously. Key activities include outreach, organisation of trainings, and tailored communication strategies to align with the needs of various scientific domains.

We will further formalise and enhance the measures that started in the initialisation phase. This includes our weekly Onboarding Open Hour, primarily targeted at service providers potentially interested in connecting to the central hub. A comparable open hour for end users of the service has just been established. In the future, we will contribute to the outreach activities organised by Base4NFDI, such as the roadshows and the user conferences, aggregating and condensing the material developed in WPs 1-4 (D5.2). We will also continue bilateral exchange with the disciplinary consortia by presenting and discussing, for example, at their annual meetings.

As outlined in Section 3.1, we will conduct incubator projects targeting content and service providers as well as end users. WP5 will take the coordinating role of announcing the incubator cycles which are planned semi-annually, collecting information from potential participants, assigning each proposed incubator to the best-suited work package, as well as collecting and disseminating individual incubator results (M5.1).

In addition to these activities, we will focus on dedicated training for domain scientists and prospective users, again based on the materials developed in WPs 1-4. The materials will also be provided to the consortia and the basic service RDMTraining4NFDI, e.g., via the knowledge base DALIA of the section EduTrain (D5.1). We will offer to conduct trainings ourselves and participate in activities offered by the consortia. To this end, we rely on our Base4NFDI service stewards to establish connections to relevant interested communities. Based on the expertise and experience of the respective principal investigators, we will also frequently offer longer workshops “Make your work reproducible with Jupyter4NFDI” (M5.2). There, participants bring in an individual research process which they would like to render reproducible.

5.2.6 Gantt chart

	Deliverable or milestone	Y1				Y2				
		Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	
WP1 Maintenance and development of service										
D1.1	Persistent import API	■								
D1.2	BinderHub instance as part of the MyBinder Federation		■							
D1.3	FAIRJupyter				■					
M1.1	All components for content integration available				□					
M1.2	Parameterized execution of Jupyter Labs		□							
M1.3	Provide publicly available KPIs			□						
WP2 Integration of AAI (infrastructure proxy)										
M2.1	Integration of IAM infrastructure proxy		□							
M2.2	Integration of consortium specific permission structures				□					
D2.1	Documentation of entitlements and permissions					■				
D2.2	Updated documentation of entitlements and permissions								■	
WP3 Integration of additional resources										
D3.1	Extended partner tutorials				■					
D3.2	Hands-on support in onboarding external resources		■							
M3.1	Integration template repository								□	
WP4 Content integration										
D4.1	Use cases featuring fully computationally reproducible content				■					
D4.2	Domain-independent training materials for self-study				■					
D4.3	Domain-specific adaptation of the materials						■			
M4.1	Initial version of the materials available				□					
M4.2	Final version of the materials available								□	
WP5 Community engagement and communication										
M5.1	First call for incubator projects		□							
D5.1	Jupyter4NFDI training material for RDMTraining4NFDI				■					
M5.2	First workshop "Make your work reproducible with Jupyter4NFDI"								□	
D5.2	Presentation material for roadshows, consortia meetings, ...			■						

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- Sheeba Samuel, Daniel Mietchen. FAIR Jupyter: A Knowledge Graph Approach to Semantic Sharing and Granular Exploration of a Computational Notebook Reproducibility Dataset. In Special Issue on Resources for Graph Data and Knowledge. Transactions on Graph Data and Knowledge (TGDK), Volume 2, Issue 2, pp. 4:1-4:24, Schloss Dagstuhl – Leibniz-Zentrum für Informatik (2024b) <https://doi.org/10.4230/TGDK.2.2.4>
- David Schoch, Chung-hong Chan, Claudia Wagner, and Arnim Bleier. Computational Reproducibility in Computational Social Science. In EPJ Data Science, Volume 13, Issue 1, Article 75, Springer (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1140/epjds/s13688-024-00514-w>
- Various commits have been prepared or already made available to JupyterHub upstream via Git Pull Requests:
 - Merged: <https://github.com/jupyterhub/jupyterhub/pull/4733>
 - Merged: <https://github.com/jupyterhub/jupyterhub/pull/4717>
 - Merged: <https://github.com/jupyterhub/jupyterhub/pull/4455>
 - In preparation: <https://github.com/jupyterhub/jupyter-server-proxy/pull/512>
 - Open: <https://github.com/jupyterhub/jupyter-server-proxy/pull/501>
 - Merged: <https://github.com/jupyterhub/jupyter-rsession-proxy/pull/159>
 - Merged: <https://github.com/jupyterhub/jupyter-rsession-proxy/pull/160>
- J. H. Göbber, T. Kreuzer, A. Grosch, A. Lintermann, and M. Riedel (2018). “Enabling Interactive Supercomputing at JSC Lessons Learned,” in Lecture Notes in Computer Science, Springer International Publishing,, pp. 669–677.
- Tim Kreuzer, & Alice Aiko Grosch (2025). kreuzert/jupyterhub-outpost: 1.0.5 (1.0.5). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14616149>
- Tim Kreuzer, & Alice Aiko Grosch (2025). kreuzert/jupyterhub-outpostspawner: 1.0.3 (1.0.3). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14616171>
- Tim Kreuzer, & Alice Aiko Grosch (2025). kreuzert/jupyterhub-unicorespawner: 1.1.1 (1.1.1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14918429>

OpenProject report of TA1 tasks

Basic Service Jupyter4NFDI

Arbeitspakete

Björn Hagemeyer-Jupyter4NFDI

Arbeitspakete

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1.1. Jupyter4NFDI / D1.4.1 (TA1): Documentation of requirements analysis	2
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1. Reporting

ID	13137	TYP	Phase
STATUS	In progress	AUFWAND	
VERBLEIBENDER AUFWAND		% ABGESCHLOSSEN	75

1.1. Jupyter4NFDI / D1.4.1 (TA1): Documentation of requirements analysis

ID	12367	TYP	Task
STATUS	Completed	AUFWAND	
VERBLEIBENDER AUFWAND		% ABGESCHLOSSEN	100

Beschreibung

TA1 instructions on [Zenodo](#)

Mapping & status table

Task	Milestones & Deliverables of Jupyter4NFDI	Status	Outcome
Jupyter4NFDI survey	M4.1, D5.1, D5.2	completed	Report on GitHub [1]

Comprehensive summary

The Jupyter4NFDI Survey was designed and conducted to gauge the current state of Jupyter usage within the NFDI consortia and to gather feedback on the Jupyter4NFDI project. In total, 75 people from 53 German research institutions participated in the user survey between Nov. 28th 2024 and Jan. 6th 2025. This report provides an overview of the survey results, with respect to the participants, their current usage of Jupyter, and their expectations from the Jupyter4NFDI project. The results contribute to developing the Jupyter4NFDI infrastructures in accordance with the requirements and expectations of the NFDI community. They will also enable the Jupyter4NFDI consortium to consolidate efforts and resources within the NFDI and, if applicable, outside collaborators.

[1]

https://gesiscss.github.io/Jupyter4NFDI_survey_results/Jupyter4NFDI%20Survey%20Summary.html

1.2. Jupyter4NFDI / D1.4.2 (TA1): Documentation of software evaluation

ID	12368	TYP	Task
STATUS	Completed	AUFWAND	
VERBLEIBENDER AUFWAND		% ABGESCHLOSSEN	100

Beschreibung

TA1 instructions on [Zenodo](#)

Mapping & status table

Task	Milestones & Deliverables of Jupyter4NFDI	Status	Outcome
Evaluation of the JupyterHub software	M1.1	Completed	A thorough evaluation of the software to be used was carried out in preparation for the initialisation phase. The software had been in use at partner JSC's facilities for several years before the application for the initialization phase. It has been found to be suitable to connect various backend resources at the same time, avoiding a need for individual JupyterHubs per resource or resource type. This approach is central to the over project.
Publication of the Jupyter4NFDI-Service Proposal	-	Completed	Publication of the Jupyter4NFDI service proposal as part of the documentation process of the software evaluation [1].
External software stack components: OpenStack, Kubernetes, Fleet, JupyterHub	M2.1	Completed	Whereas there are several ways to deploy JupyterHub services in production, the software stack involving the components mentioned here has proven to be stable and of high utility at JSC. These externally developed components meet the demands of numerous parties ranging from academia to industry.
UNICORE	M2.1	Completed	UNICORE, originally developed at JSC for more than 25 years together with German and European partners, is a crucial component to integrate HPC resources in a JupyterHub deployment.

JupyterHub OutpostSpawner and Outpost	M1.1	Completed	These two components make up the two ends of the integration layer between JupyterHub and generic external resources. A lightweight communication layer allows for almost arbitrary deployments of Jupyter Notebook services at the external resources.
IAM4NFDI	M1.1	Completed	This central service within Base4NFDI can be taken for granted. Coincidentally, it is based on the same software stack that has already been in use at JSC for years, such that we are confident to be able to do the integration.

Comprehensive summary

Jupyter4NFDI has not been developed as a greenfield project. There has been a precursor running at JSC for several years, from which we also inherited some of the versatility of the central hub regarding the connection to backend resources of various types. Based on this solid foundation, we further extended the ability to integrate various external resources. This will include, but is not limited to HPC resources available within NHR, generic Cloud computing resources, e.g. from an NFDI Multi-Cloud.

The service stack has been crafted in such a way, that it will be scalable and cater for serving many simultaneous users, certainly in the hundreds.

[1] <https://zenodo.org/records/12699382>

1.3. Jupyter4NFDI / D1.4.3 (TA1): Documentation of service design

ID	12369	TYP	Task
STATUS	Completed	AUFWAND	
VERBLEIBENDER AUFWAND		% ABGESCHLOSSEN	100

Beschreibung

From TA1 instructions on [Zenodo](#)

Mapping & status table

Task	Milestones & Deliverables of DMP4NFDI	Status	Outcome
Deployment of central JupyterHub	M1.1, D1.1	completed	The Jupyter4NFDI service documentation has been created [1]

Resource Manager	M2.1, D2.1	completed	The JupyterHub Outpost architecture has been documented [2]
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Comprehensive summary

Comprehensive service documentation for the Jupyter4NFDI basic service was created as part of the initialisation phase [1]. The documentation contains a general explanation of the service and is aimed at both users of the service and service providers who want to connect external resources to the central Jupyter Hub.

Understanding the JupyterHub Outpost architecture will help set up and manage Outpost instances effectively, while ensuring your resources remain secure. The JupyterHub Outpost architecture has been described in a new chapter of the Jupyter4NFDI service documentation [2].

[1] <https://nfdi-jupyter.de/>

[2] <https://nfdi-jupyter.de/providers/architecture/>

1.4. Jupyter4NFDI / D1.4.4 (TA1): Service prototype

ID	13135	TYP	Task
STATUS	Completed	AUFWAND	
VERBLEIBENDER AUFWAND		% ABGESCHLOSSEN	100

Beschreibung

TA1 instructions on [Zenodo](#)

Mapping & status table

Task	Milestones & Deliverables of DMP4NFDI	Status	Outcome
Deployment of central JupyterHub	M1.1, D1.1	completed	The service prototype has been made available at [1]
Resource Manager	M2.1, D2.1	completed	JSC resources have been made available in central Jupyter4NFDI hub [1]. Blueprint for deploying a JupyterHub Outpost (aka external Resources) via Helm Chart [3]
Integration of the AAI	M3.1, D3.1	completed	Authentication is already possible via Helmholtz Login [1]. Continuing IAM4NFDI incubator project for connecting service to IAM Infra Proxy [2] has started.

Comprehensive summary

The service prototype has been made available at <https://hub.nfdi-jupyter.de/> along with documentation for **users** and interested **resource providers**. Authentication is currently possible via Helmholtz Login, which is an integral part of IAM4NFDI. We are waiting for the IAM4NFDI infrastructure proxy to become available and will connect to it. To this end, we have applied as an incubator project to the IAM4NFDI project.

Helmholtz Login does not limit authentication to only users from the Helmholtz Association, but also allows for using all eduGAIN (excluding Russian and Belarussian) and social IdPs.

[1] <https://hub.nfdi-jupyter.de/>

[2] <https://incubators.nfdi-aa.de/>

[3] <https://gitlab.jsc.fz-juelich.de/jupyterjsc/denbi-deployments/-/tree/jupyter-outpost>

1.5. Jupyter4NFDI / D1.4.5 (TA1): Service piloting and user testing

ID	13136	TYP	Task
STATUS	In progress	AUFWAND	
VERBLEIBENDER AUFWAND		% ABGESCHLOSSEN	50

Beschreibung

TA1 instructions on [Zenodo](#)

Mapping & status table

Task	Milestones & Deliverables of Jupyter4NFDI	Status	Outcome
Deployment of central JupyterHub, Resource Manager	M1.1, M2.1	completed	Central JupyterHub deployed and resources have been made available (see D1.4.4). Communities of NFDI consortia have started pilot testing and usage of the available resources [2], [3], [4], [5], [6], [7], [8], [9]
Connecting external resources	M4.1		Initial external resources have been made available in staging environment of central hub [1].

Comprehensive summary

Consortia integration

In Text+, one of the participating consortia, the Jupyter4NFDI service is being used regularly for at least one use case: The Fluffy Import [5]. This involves a notebook-based application [6] for - among other things - importing data in TextGridRep [7], a repository of great relevance for the humanities, which is optimised for TEI-XML data and allows the publication of text and images. The notebook-based approach replaces the initial import and publication system, which became hard to maintain and update. The NFDI JupyterHub is the recommended platform for running the application, and a link to a preconfigured environment based on a Docker image is provided in the readme of the code repository.

The service has also recently been used in the workshop "TEI-Dokumente in TextGrid Repository veröffentlichen und archivieren: neue Features und fluffiger Import Workflow" [8], where it proved very useful and worked as expected.

Furthermore, the service is being showcased and recommended repeatedly in the bi-weekly meeting "Text+ Show and Tell" [9], where it also was the main topic of the kickoff meeting.

Other projects have manifested interest and are expected to use the service.

- NFDI4Ing

Together with NFDI4Ing we were able to show applicability of our generic solution for at least one use case of the *11th Society of Petroleum Engineers Comparative Solution Project* [2]. At the time of setting up this scenario, we needed to import a dataset to Jupyter4NFDI at JSC to make it available within Jupyter Labs there. Since then, we have developed a method to generically import data from external repositories, such that a migration of data prior to execution will not be needed anymore provided that it is available from another service. As can be seen in the repository, it directly links to an executable Jupyter environment in Jupyter4NFDI.

- FlowR [3]

Validation with user groups

The group of Prof. Martin Pfeleiderer at the University of Music Franz Liszt Weimar was able to immediately make use of the central Jupyter4NFDI service for their use case involving an open-source software toolbox for sheet music annotation, statistical analysis, visualization, and pattern search operations. This is actually our expectation for many standard use cases that do not have particular demands. As a matter of fact, because Jupyter4NFDI allows for using custom images, we believe to be able to accommodate a wide range of user demands even if they have very specific software requirements.

- *MaRDI*
- *NFDI4Biodiversity (Seeger)*
- *Fluffy Import (Text+)*
- *4DS*

Connecting external resources

Besides validating the service applicability with *end users*, we have validated our approach to integrate *external resources* with several *resource providers*. The natural choice for resources were those at JSC for which a precursor already existed with the Jupyter JSC offering. Through this integration, we were able to provide access to the JSC Cloud computing resources. Furthermore, Cloud resources at MPCDF and de.NBI Cloud have been integrated in the staging environment [1] with resources at MPCDF ready to be added to the production environment. Another type of resources is under way provided by TU Dresden. Following the template of JSC's approach to integrating HPC resources in JupyterHub, resources at TU Dresden, which in turn will serve as a template for the integration of other NHR resources. Further integrations are planned with the University of Stuttgart, where a Kubernetes cluster is currently set up.

Demonstration of general applicability

Without consideration of individual use cases or user groups, the number of unique users per period (day, week, month) is increasing on average, as can be seen by the numbers we gathered between 2024-06-26 and 2025-04-09 [10].

References

- [1] JupyterHub staging environment <https://hub-staging.nfdi-jupyter.de/>
- [2] <https://github.com/Simulation-Benchmarks/11thSPE-CSP>
- [3] <https://github.com/Code-Inspect/binder-flowR>
- [4] https://www.hfm-weimar.de/en/working/professors-teachers/lehre-detail?tx_jobbase_pi3%5Baction%5D=orgadetail&tx_jobbase_pi3%5Bcontroller%5D=Elements&tx_jobbase_pi3%5BjoOrgaDetail%5D=106&tx_jobbase_pi3%5BjoRefererId%5D=220&cHash=ae2d

f9e057049ac2a5c4cb507a9ddaac

- [5] <https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/workflow/iqj7B6>
- [6] <https://gitlab.gwdg.de/textplus/textplus-io/nb-actions>
- [7] <https://textgridrep.org>
- [8] https://dhd2025.dig-hum.de/?page_id=8
- [9] <https://events.gwdg.de/category/286/>
- [10] <https://zenodo.org/records/15187218>

1.6. Jupyter4NFDI / (TA1): Presentation of final results in section meeting

ID	13389	TYP	Task
STATUS	To be scheduled	AUFWAND	
VERBLEIBENDER AUFWAND		% ABGESCHLOSSEN	0

Beschreibung

Presentation of final results in section meeting

TA1 instructions

Should be done, but is not a hard requirement

When done provide link to minutes and slides.